

Automatic detection and identification of invasive arthropod pests for pest management and biosecurity

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Abstract

Thousands of insect traps are deployed both in border surveillance and integrated pest management programmes, all of which need to be checked manually to obtain any data on insect populations. As an alternative to this form of surveillance program we offer an automated system comprised of optical sensors and precise machine learning algorithms provide accurate identification and counts of trapped insects. This is achieved through the use of pseudo acoustic data derived from the wingbeat of the insect as it enters the trap. We are working to build a library of wing beat frequency data of relevant insects for the Asia Pacific region to be used with the FarmSense algorithm, and will be testing this technology on farms and within border monitoring operations in the near future.

Background

The field of entomology has long been long starved of automation, with classical manual techniques of monitoring behaviour and identification of species still prevalent in research and in IPM programs. Camera traps have added some level of automation to the field but issues with reliability, efficiency and cost have led to limited uptake. The concept of using wing beat frequency has long been considered a valid approach (Kahn 1945 et al), but the use of microphones to capture this data acoustically has limited its development into a useable system. Microphones are inherently limited in the range at which they can pick up sounds as faint as the flapping of a single insect wings as sound is an inverse square law force. They are also susceptible to background noise from the environment. The concept of optically recording wing beat frequency allows this concept to progress. Richards (1955) first reports this pseudo-acoustic recording of wing beat frequency by using a photocell pointed directly at the sun and recording the disruption of sunlight caused by insects passing over the cell. Moore (1986) improved on this using a photosensor based on an optical tachometer and demonstrated its ability to identify and sort species of aphids and aphid parasitoids in the lab using cluster analysis and artificial neural networks (Moore and Miller 2002).

Eammon Keogh and his team at the University of California Riverside, armed with expertise in machine learning and Bayesian statistics are now developing a cost effective and reliable tool for insect classification (Chen et al 2014). It is based on a pair of near infrared emitters and receivers, such that when the light beam is disrupted the resulting waveform is recorded by a networked microcontroller, and can be either analysed in situ or sent out over the network for remote analysis. While current iterations of this sensor are limited to their use within pre-existing insect traps, it has potential to be applied in a number of different configurations. Plant and Food Research have partnered with FarmSense to develop the wing beat libraries necessary for the algorithm that powers the system for integrated pest management (IPM) and biosecurity applications in New Zealand and the Asia Pacific region. Plant and Food Research will also be testing and aiding in the design of the device to ensure that it is fit for purpose.

Methods

All adult insects were reared from laboratory colonies derived from wild individuals collected at various locations. *Aedes aegypti* (Yellowfever mosquito) were reared in enamel pans under standard laboratory conditions (27°C, 16:8 h light:dark [LD] cycle with 1 hour dusk/dawn periods) and fed ad libitum on a mixture of ground rodent chow and Brewer's yeast (3:1, v:v). *Musca domestica* (Housefly) larvae were kept under standard laboratory conditions (12:12 h [LD] cycle, 26°C, 40% RH) and reared

in a mixture of water, bran meal, alfalfa, yeast, and powdered milk. *Drosophila simulans* (Fruitfly) larvae were fed ad libitum on a mixture of rotting fruit.

Wing beat frequencies were obtained using the FarmSense sensor placed inside an insect enclosure, containing approximately 30 to 40 insects to maximize the number of recordings while minimizing the chance of two insects passing through the sensor at the same time

Low frequencies were attenuated to decrease the amount of non-wing beat frequency related noise recording from insects walking through the sensor rather than flying. When the sensor detected a signal greater than the preprogrammed threshold, the analogue signal from the sensor was written into a csv file which was converted from the time domain to the frequency domain via fast fourier transformation for further analysis. The data was scored on the amplitude of the primary harmonic and definition of the harmonic peaks within the frequency domain data. Those signals deemed to be of sufficient quality were included in the library and used to aid the classification of future data.

Results

Figure 1 displays an example of the raw time series signal recorded from the sensor (left) as well as the same signal transformed to the frequency domain to give the frequency values of the harmonics within the signals waveform, the lowest being the primary harmonic. In figure 2 the distribution of primary harmonic frequencies of three species (*A. aegypti*, *D. simulans* and *M. domestica*) can be observed, each plot representing 1000 wingbeat sound snippets from each species.

Figure 1. An Example of a single wingbeat sound snippet of a *Drosophila simulans*

Figure 2: (Top) Histograms of wingbeat frequencies of three species of insects, *A. aegypti*, *D. simulans* and *M. domestica*. Each histogram is derived from 1,000 wingbeat sound snippets. (Bottom) Gaussian curves that fit the wingbeat frequency histograms.

Discussion

The primary harmonic wing beat frequencies were able to distinguish between some species, but not all (Figure 2). However, as we see in the plots of *Drosophila simulans* and *Musca domestica* there can be overlaps between species. This challenge could be overcome with the use of species-specific lures, by behavioural variations within species in response to time of day, temperature and barometric pressure, or by geolocation of the sensor. Chen (2014) also reported on the ability to distinguish the sexes of mosquitos. Even without species-specific identification, the system still provides a level of automation to insect motoring that will be of use in biosecurity applications to alert operators for timely responses to insect incursions.

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